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D2.2 – User manuals on agent configuration and execution

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Executive Summary

This document comprises the deliverable D2.2 that describes the MAS4AI approach to agents parametrization, configuration and execution. The core part of the approach is the agents' self-description capabilities through their Asset Administration Shells (AAS). Each agent has the standardized AAS with the specific submodels that are used for agent's configuration and parametrization. A special type of agent is developed, called Agent Management System (AMS), that serves as an interface between a user of the system and its agents. The AMS agent provides configuration, parametrization and lifecycle services for the system's users, as well as for the other I4.0 components, through its AAS.

First, a short overview of the state-of-the-art MAS frameworks regarding their parametrization and configuration services is given. Then the requirements for the parametrization and configuration are specified, as well as extensions to the standard agents AAS. The description of the approach is given next together with the UML class diagram of the concept. The major submodels of the AAS for the AMS agent are described next. The list of the use-case diagrams serve as the manuals for the developers to implement the fully functional service complying with the requirements, defined in the deliverable. The last section provides two prototype implementations of the concept, which serve as the feasibility check and the bootstrap examples for the developers.

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1 Introduction

The main objective of this document is to describe the approach of the MAS4AI project to the parametrization, configuration and execution services of the MAS system. The approach utilizes the agents' self-description capabilities provided by their AASs. Each agent is described by the standardized AAS with the specific submodels focusing on parametrization and configuration. By providing all the information needed for parametrization and configuration through the AASs it is possible to avoid using implicit, solution specific configuration, which is normally provided from the proprietary configuration files. The standard AAS API ensures the unified service-oriented access to the parametrisation services.

Another part of the MAS4AI parameterization and execution service is the new agent type that focuses on the system management and agents' lifecycle. The name of the new agent, Agent Management System, was taken from the FIPA standard to emphasize its scope and functionalities. The agent serves as an interface between the users of the system and the agents that constitute the solution. The AMS agent also has its own AAS and can configure itself at the start of the system. After the start-up it provides the user with the services to activate/deactivate the required agent, as well as with the other agent's lifecycle related functionalities.

The user manuals for the developers are provided in the form of the major use-case diagrams, description of the AMS AAS, class diagram of the service, as well as two prototypical implementation examples to bootstrap the development of the solutions.

2 Analysis of the existing MAS tools

In this section, we consider existing approaches of the FIPA-Standard as well as tool approaches for this functionality.

2.1 Agent Management System according to FIPA

To ensure interoperability between agents, the Foundation for Intelligent Physical Agents (FIPA) has developed a set of standards. The aim is to enable agents to exchange information with each other. In this regard, FIPA represents an international non-profit association of companies and organizations that work together to create specifications for generic agent technologies. FIPA promotes a set of generic technologies for multiple application domains which can be used by developers to create a high degree of interoperability in complex systems. To this end, normative rules were created at the outset to enable agents to exist, operate, and be managed. From these developed standards come the Communicative Acts Library and the Agent Communication Language (ACL). These represent a standard for the communication between agents in a multi-agent system. [1]

2.1.1 Agent Platform and Agent Management Reference Model

To provide an agent platform, the following reference model, as shown on **Figure 1** for an agent platform and on **Figure 2** for agent management, were developed. The entities are logical capability sets (i.e., services) and do not imply physical components. Implementation details regarding the individual agent platforms (AP) and the individual agents can be made independently by the developers of the corresponding agent system.

Figure 1 FIPA Reference Model for an Agent Platform, according to [2]

The FIPA Reference Model for agent management is shown on **Figure 2**.

Figure 2 Agent Management Reference Model, according to [3]

Based on the related literature, the elements of the reference model for an Agent Platform consist of three main components [1], [2], [3], [4], [5].

1. The Agent Management System (AMS) is the agent that monitors access to and uses the platform and requires registration in the AMS to obtain an Agent Identifier (AID). The AID contains the defined agent username and IP address, and the AMS thus acts as a central directory where agents can register themselves, query information about other agents, and is used to manage their life cycle. The “Yellow Pages service” of the AMS is an essential service to the agents and is based on a list of agents, identified by their GUID (globally unique identifier), which allows unique localization within the system. These agents are thus registered in the agent platform.
2. The Agent Communications Channel (ACC) provides the path for communication between agents inside and outside the platform and can be seen as the default communication method that provides a reliable, orderly, and accurate message forwarding service.
3. The Directory Facilitator (DF) is the agent that forwards the Yellow Page services to the agent platform. For realization of the agent platform, there are no restrictions to specific technologies. To know what services can be offered by agents, they can register or query their various services in the DF.

To find other agents in the system, an agent can send a query message to the AMS, with the information to specify the type of agent it is looking for and furthermore other relevant criteria. The AMS then searches in its directory and returns a list of agents, which are matching the criteria of the query. In addition to registration and discovery, the AMS also provides other services such as agent deletion and modification. When an agent wants to leave the system, it sends a message to the AMS, so that is also could be removed from the directory. When an agent needs to update its information, it can send a message for changing the information to the AMS. The AMS in FIPA provide thus a standardized way for agents to register and find other agents in a multi-agent system, enabling efficient communication and collaboration.

2.1.2 Agent Communication Channel and AMS

In Figure 3, the sequence flow between Agent Communication Channel (ACC) and the AMS is presented, based on the setup in [4].

Figure 3 Sequence Flow between Agent Communication Channel and Agent Management System, according to [4]

Based on the FIPA-Standards an Agent Platform must at least provide two functional agents. Therefore, one needs an ACC and an AMS that strictly interact with each other [6], [7], [8]. The ACC acts as a message router of an Agent Platform. Regarding ACC requests, it could be differentiated between implicit and explicit requests.

2.1.3 Agent-based management-functions of an AMS

Based on the FIPA-Standard in [3] the AMS represents an important component in an Agent Framework, due to the task of observation and management of all agents inside of the framework. This subsection refers to the FIPA-Standard in [3].

The AMS must provide the following functions:

- Register
- Deregister
- Change
- Search
- Receive Description

Furthermore, the AMS can give commands to the Agent Platform, to process the following operations:

- Suspend an agent
- Terminate an agent
- Create an agent
- Resume the agent execution
- Invoke an agent
- Execute an agent
- Resource Management

In addition to registration and recognition, the AMS provides services such as deletion and modification of agents. As mentioned above, the AMS in FIPA provides a way for agents to register and find other agents in a multi-agent system. This enables agents to achieve efficient communication and collaboration between agents.

2.2 Agent Management System functions in Jade

The Java Agent Development Framework (Jade) is among the most widely used agent frameworks. JADE can be considered as a reference implementation from the FIPA specifications and is implemented in Java. The framework facilitates the development of agent specifications

in compliance with the FIPA specifications to ensure interoperability of multi-agent systems [2], [9].

JADE agents run on their own thread and have their own message interface to receive messages from other agents. Thus, JADE agents can either implement FIPA ACL or consider simple serialized JAVA objects. When using JADE, it is not necessary to start the AMS manually. The AMS is started by default when the agent platform is started in JADE. During this process, the agents are automatically registered, which provides them with their unique AID [5].

Furthermore, JADE offers a simplified implementation of MAS systems with graphical tools and user interfaces. JADE also offers the possibility to add a "sniffer" agent. This can monitor the messages between selected agents and another. These are then displayed together with the exchanged messages in a graphical user interface. [5]

Figure 4 shows such a sniffer agent, as shown in [5].

Figure 4 Sniffer-Agent of Jade, according to [5]

3 Requirements for the MAS4AI parametrization and configuration service

In this section we list the requirements for the functionalities that are to be provided by the execution and parametrization service of the MAS4AI platform. Three levels of obligation are considered according to [10]:

- Shall – an object must implement the function;
- Should – an object will, if it is possible, implement the function;
- Will – an object may implement the function at some point in future;

3.1 Requirements for the Configuration Service

3.1.1 Agents' life-cycle

A service *shall* provide the agents' life-cycle functionalities. The minimum set of the life-cycle services are:

1. Initial setup of a single agent.
 - A system user shall be able to choose the required agent type from the pallet of provided by the system.
 - A system shall enable the parametrisation of the agent, if the parameters are needed.
2. Activation/deactivation of an agent.
 - A system user shall be able to activate the chosen agent type.
 - A system user shall be able to deactivate the running agent. Hard and soft deactivation options shall be provided:
 - *Soft deactivation* should stop the agent immediately if possible or wait till the agent completes its current task.
 - *Hard deactivation* shall immediately deactivate the agent. *Note*: the system performance may degrade because of this action.
3. Reboot an agent.

- A system user will be able to reboot the agent. *Note:* This can be achieved by sequentially executing deactivation and activation commands.
4. Monitor agent's state.
- A system shall provide services to monitor an agent's current state variables.

3.1.2 Topology configuration

A service shall provide MAS topology configuration. By topology configuration we mean setting the relationships between the agents in the holon. Different control structures can be achieved: heterarchical, modified hierarchies or strong hierarchy.

3.1.3 System configuration.

A system shall provide a set of services to configure itself.

1. A service will provide a user-friendly API for MAS4AI platform customization.
2. A service will provide the tools for configuration of external services.
3. A system should provide the means for configuration of communication channels with the external systems, if these channels are used by the agents.

3.2 Requirements for the Parametrization Service

3.2.1 Parametrization of agent's algorithms

A service shall enable parametrization of agents' algorithms. Depending on the algorithm an agent might need parametrization and finetuning. Parameters of the algorithm shall be part of the agent's AAS or the AAS of the algorithm itself.

1. A system shall enable setting of the algorithm's parameters, computing modes, etc.
2. A system should enable setting the timeout for executing a task by an agent.

3.2.2 Parameters checking

The correctness of the parameters shall be checked before agent's initialization.

- 1) A service should check type and range of the agent's parameters. *Note:* Parameters attributes, such as type, range, etc. shall be provided in the AAS to enable their check.

- 2) A service will check the meaning of the giving parameters by using their semanticIDs.
Note: to enable this feature the semanticIDs to correct vocabularies shall be given in the AAS.
- 3) A system will implement contract-based verification of parameters and conditions before starting an agent.

3.3 Extension of the standard agent submodels

Within the given framework every agent follows a general structure when modelled to create a uniform homogenous representation. The approach used is described in the work of Nikolova and Rongen [11]. There is a set of standard submodels provided, which can be used as a base to create every agent. We propose an extension of these submodels, based on the requirements provided by the framework in which the agent would exist.

Originally it was defined that the agent needs to have a submodel called *Configuration Parameters*, which encapsulates all the relevant information needed to initialize and connect. This is now split in two different submodels – one for *Parameterization* and one for *Configuration*.

3.3.1 Parameterization

The parameterization submodel contains information which is local for the agent and describes all the relevant parameters, which need to be defined right before or at the spawning of the agent, so that it has the desired range of functions and is able to function properly. This contains information such as a set of given *Preconditions* (e.g. *max_iterations* or *decision_threshold*), *Message Templates* etc. Overall, this aims to gather at one spot all the information of this type.

Name	Type	Value From	Description
Timeout	Submodel Element Collection	User/Other Program	Describes the parameters that defines a predetermined period of time that the agent will wait for the execution of its action.
Input-Output Parameters	Submodel Element Collection	User/Other Program	Describes a set of parameters which are used when determining the needed specifications for the input and the output of the agent (can have different format, depending on what is needed at the given case)

Preconditions	Submodel Element Collection	User/Other Program	The preconditions gather any relevant parameters determined by the use case/ situation in which the agent is used.
Message Templates	Submodel Element Collection	User/Other Program	Specifies the type of messages that the agent can send/receive and provides any extra relevant properties needed for this.

Table 1 Parameterization submodel elements.

The population of this submodel with variety of properties and corresponding data is executed at two different steps of the development process:

- *During development:* The developers of the agent algorithm determine during the creation process what are the set of relevant parameters, which are needed for the agent to be set up and initialized.
- *Prior to deployment:* The values of the actual parameters are determined by the use case/ situation in which the algorithm is used and are defined prior or at the moment of the agent spawn. This information can come from a user, agent management system or other relevant program.

3.3.2 Configuration

The configuration submodel contains information which is considered to be global – it is defined by the framework used and the corresponding agent management system. It provides a way for a spawned agent to gather all the relevant information needed for the system at once. Therefore, this submodel contains three main collections – *MAS System Configuration*, *Topology Configuration*, *Lifecycle Services*. Depending on the level and tasks of the agent, the extensivity of the information in each of this submodels varies – only what is relevant to the agent is kept in this submodel.

Name	Type	Value From	Description
MAS System Configuration	Submodel Element Collection	Defined by the MAS4AI framework and management agent	Describes components such as <i>Communication</i> , <i>System Services</i> etc.
Topology Configuration	Submodel Element Collection		Describes configuration information on the structure of the systems foundation (holon configuration, agent types,

			dependencies, topological structure)
Lifecycle Services	Submodel Element Collection		Provides information regarding different relevant properties for the agent's lifecycle

Table 2 General components of the configuration submodel.

Every one of the three collections define above can contain different set of information depending on what is needed. When it comes to the *Lifecycle Services*, there is a set of predefined properties, which are commonly relevant – *Status*, *SpawnedAt*, *SpawnedBy*, *Assignments*.

Name	Type	Value From	Description
Agent Status	Property	AMS agent/Other Program	Indication of the current status of the agent (e.g. <i>Suspended</i>)
SpawnedAt	Property	AMS agent/Other Program	Notes the moment the agent was spawned within the current framework
SpawnedBy	Property	AMS agent/Other Program	Notes the program/agent the agent was spawned by within the current framework
Assignments	Submodel Element Collection	AMS agent/Other Program	Describes the type of assignments that the agent needs to fulfil in the form of properties (e.g. <i>ScheduleOrders</i>)

Table 3 Lifecycle Services submodel element collection

The population of those submodels happens at the moment of deployment of the agent and throughout its working process (as values such as *Status* update continuously). The exact properties and submodels are defined during the creation of the framework and agent management system.

4 Concept of the MAS4AI parametrization and execution service

In this section we give a high level description of the MAS4AI parametrization and configuration service.

4.1 Assets self-description capability

The concept of self-description of assets via standard AASs is essential for the parametrization and execution service of MAS4AI framework. Every asset in the system has its asset administration shell with set of standard submodels. In the MAS4AI we do not use AAS submodels to directly control the assets. Instead, we use the information provided by such models to configure the communication channels needed to interact with these assets

Figure 5 Self-description of assets as a basis for interoperability

Agents utilize this by configuring themselves on how to interact with the other agents, with the production modules or how to use the external algorithms. Figure 5 schematically shows how self-description of assets can be used by the agents. On the figure every asset is connected to its AAS via some AAS middleware (the green arrows). In the MAS4AI a Basyx and a Dimofac middlewares are used. Each agent as a functionality to use the standard AAS REST API. The agents use their knowledge of the *assetInterfaceDescription* submodel, which will be described later, to get the required information about the communication channels provided by the asset (blue arrows). The agents use this information to automatically connect to the assets, provided they have these capabilities (red arrows).

4.2 Agent Management System

FIPA standard defines an *Agent Management System (AMS)* as a mandatory component of every agent system. It provides a supervisory control over the use of the platform. It provides so called white pages services to the agents. It holds the repository of the agent's addresses and each agent must register itself with the AMS to get the valid agent's ID.

A *Directory Facilitator (DF)* provides yellow pages services to the other agents. Agents register their services with the DF and can find out what services are provided by the other agents. In our project we use the more abstract term capability to describe a possible functionality of an entity, i.e. an intelligent agent. The holonic agents register their capabilities with the DF agent.

In MAS4AI framework there is also an *Agent Management System (AMS)*. This role is given to a special agent – AMS Agent. The AMS agent provides the administrative services and serves as a single point for the system supervision. All the services provided by this agent are described in its AAS as skills and capabilities. Capabilities can be semantically defined in some vocabulary using SemanticIDs. Skills are implemented by AAS operations and can be accessed using the standard AAS REST API. All the information services, such as agent's repository or monitoring are also available through the AMS Agent AAS. The AMS Agent's submodels will be described in the section 5.

Figure 6 shows the class diagram of the MAS4AI execution and parametrization service, realized by the AMS Agent together with its AAS. When the system starts it spawns only one holon, specifically the AMS Agent. It connects to its AAS and configures itself to listen to the specific control topics. For the Basyx AAS middleware we have chosen Kafka and for the Dimofac Digital Platform – MQTT messaging middleware. All these settings are defined in the *assetInterfaceDescription* of the agent's AAS. As the class diagram shows, in order to communicate through the required channels, an agent should set the appropriate skills. Each agent in the framework has a basic skill to communicate via REST-like web interface to be able to interact with the AASs. Only the AMS Agent can administer the other agents in the system. The basic operations would be parameterize, spawn, kill an agent. The AAS of the AMS agent is the only access point to the functionalities of the AMS Agent. It makes the AMS AAS effectively the interface the MAS4AI execution and parametrization service. This separates the UI-specific software from the MAS4AI framework through the standard AAS metamodel and REST API.

Figure 6 Execution and Parametrisation Service class diagram.

5 Asset Administration Shell for the AMS agent

As it was already stated earlier the AAS of the AMS Agent plays the central role in providing the standard interface and information services to the users of the system. In this section we describe the most important submodules of the AMS AAS. Figure 7 shows the AAS Explorer with the AMS AAS.

Figure 7 AAS of AMS Agent in the AAS Explorer

As the AMS Agent AAS inherits from the common MAS4AI agent AAS model it has all the standard submodels, such as Identification, Nameplate, MAS4AI_Agent.

5.1 BillOfMaterial

Each holonic agent, i.e. an agent that comprises other agents, has a submodel that describes its configuration or topology. This submodel is not strictly a BillOfMaterial model, because the later describes only hierarchical relations between its components. The former may have the relationship components other then isPartOf, as it can be seen on Figure 8.

Figure 8 BillOfMaterials Graph as a MAS4AI Holon Topology Configuration

The BillOfMaterials name was chosen to enable the graph visualisation capabilities of the AASX explorer.

At the system’s start the AMS Agent reads the BillOfMaterials submodel to get the information on which other agents should be spawned. If an agent for spawning is itself a holon then it also has a BillOfMaterial and spawns its own agents.

5.2 Capabilities and Skills

Being a MAS4AI agent the AMS Agent also has a set of capabilities that are listed in this submodel. Each capability is described by the capability element, which semanticID references the vocabulary for semantic description of this capability. Another element of this model is the reference element that points to the skill that implements this capability.

The agent’s skills are listed in the Skills submodel. Each skill is implemented by the operation that can be called by the AAS REST API. To support agent’s self-configuration a skill element has also a reference to the particular element of the assetInterfaceDescription. On the **Figure 9** an *ActivateAgent* skill has a reference *SkillBinding* that points to the *SubmodelElementCollection* *ActivateAgent* event. This event description provides all the information needed to agent to connect to the backend.

Figure 9 Skill binding through the assetInterfaceDescription

5.3 AssetInterfaceDescription submodel

The `assetInterfaceDescription` submodel¹ is the standard submodel provided by the IDTA association². This submodel is based on the W3C Web of Thing Description³ (TD) that uses web standards to uniformly describe the IoT devices. A TD provides the information on how data and functions of the device are provided, which protocol is used and how data is encoded and structured.

¹ <https://github.com/admin-shell-io/submodel-templates/tree/main/development/Asset%20Interface%20Description/1/0>

² <https://industrialdigitaltwin.org/en/>

³ <https://www.w3.org/WoT/>

We use the `assetInterfaceDescription` submodel to provide an agent the information on how it can connect and use the communication channels. This submodel also describes the interfaces to the resources, i.e. CPPMs, to support self-configuration scenarios. As an example, **Figure 9** shows the binding of the `ActivateAgent` skill to the two Dimofac-specific mqtt topics. The description of this binding will be described in the section 7.2.

Figure 10 Agent Lifecyle submodel

5.4 Lifecycle

The concept of agent’s lifecycle was taken from the FIPA standard⁴. The agent’s states are used by the AMS service during activation/deactivation of the agent. The realization of lifecycle state machine depends on the software agent platform and in the MAS4AI framework not all the states are currently implemented. Because we are not committed to a particular agent platform

⁴ <http://www.fipa.org/specs/fipa00023/SC00023J.html>

we foresee the use of different lifecycle state machines. That is why there is a property *TypeOfStateMachine* in the Lifecycle submodel. **Figure 10** shows the Lifecycle submodel of the AMS Agent with the FIPA state machine. SubmodelCollectionElement States list all possible states of the state machine, transitions between the states are modeled as relationship elements with the reference *Trigger* to enable the transition. The submodel also provides the properties *CurrentState* and *LastTransition* for complete monitoring of the state machine.

5.5 AgentsRegistry and AgentTypes

FIPA standard defines AMS and Directory Facilitator responsible for registering and holding information about the active agents in the system. In MAS4AI the AAS of the AMS Agent serves as a single source of such information, which exist in two submodels – AgentRegistry and AgentTypes (see **Figure 11**).

Figure 11 AgentRegistry and AgentTypes Submodels

Before initializing a new agent the AMS Agent register the AAS of its agent to the *AgentRegistry* submodel, so all the AASs of the active agents are holed there. Before the agent’s deactivation the agent is removed from the submodel.

The *AgentsTypes* submodel holds all the agent types that can be activated and used in the system. Each agent type submodel element holds the reference to the AAS of that agent type. It may also have the semanticId of the respective agent to give the user semantic information about this agent. The AMS Agent use the reference to get the AAS of the requested agent for the

required parameters. After deploying the new agent type to the systems it should also be registered in the AgentTypes submodel as described in section 6.3.

6 Use case diagrams of the MAS4AI parametrization and configuration service

This section describes the most common scenarios of using the execution and parameterisation service. They are defined as the UML use-case diagrams and serve as the specifications for the developers and users.

6.1 Use cases notation and specification

A use case specification is a way to textually describe a narrative that unfolds when an actor invokes a particular use case. The template used in this report is described in [12].

1. **Use case name:** a verb phrase
2. **Scope:** the entity that owns (provides) the use case (for example, the name of an organization, system, subsystem, or component)
3. **Primary actor:** the actor that invokes the use case (the actor whose goal the use case represents)
4. **Supporting (secondary) actors:** actors that provide a service to the system (participate in the use case by performing actions)
5. **Stakeholder:** someone or something with a vested interest in the behavior of the system
6. **Preconditions:** the conditions that must be true for this use case to begin
7. **Guarantees (postconditions):** the conditions that must be true at the end of the use case
8. **Trigger:** the event that gets the use case started
9. **Main success scenario:** the scenario (the sequence of steps) in which nothing goes wrong
10. **Extensions (alternative branches):** alternative sequences of steps branching off of the main success scenario
11. **Related information:** whatever your project needs for additional information

6.2 Develop and deploy agent template

Figure 12 shows the use-case diagram of the “develop and deploy agent’s template” scenario.

1. **Use case name:** Develop and deploy agent template
2. **Scope:** MAS4AI codebase, SARL IDE
3. **Primary actor:** Agent developer
4. **Supporting (secondary) actors:** AAS modelling expert, AAS Explorer, SARL IDE, Janus Runtime

5. **Stakeholder:** System user, agent developer
6. **Preconditions:** the agent’s algorithm should already be developed and tested in the framework of choice
7. **Guarantees (postconditions):** the developed agent class with all the required capacities and skills is implemented and deployed in the SARL IDE
8. **Trigger:** Solution development workflow event
9. **Main success scenario:**
 - a. The SARL developer uses the existing codebase (agents, capacities, skills classes) to develop the required agent type
 - b. The agents algorithm is integrated into the agent’s program either directly or using interfaces with the external services, following the approaches that were described in the deliverable D2.1. [13]
 - c. All the created classes should be compiled and installed with the Janus Runtime.
 - d. The AAS modelling expert created the AAS model of the agent type as well as the AAS model for the agent’s instance.
 - i. The capabilities of the agent in the AAS should correspond to the skills implemented in the agent’s program.
 - ii. The interfaces that the agent uses to communicate with the external services should be described in the AAS submodel *assetInterfaceDescription* to support agent’s self-configuration.
10. **Extensions (alternative branches):** testing and debugging of the agent’s program follows the appropriate software engineering methodic.
11. **Related information:**

Figure 12 Develop and Deploy Use Case

6.3 Register agent type

1. **Use case name:** Register agent type
2. **Scope:** Configuration and Execution Service
3. **Primary actor:** Agent developer
4. **Supporting actors:** Basyx (Dimofac), UI component
5. **Stakeholders:** System user, agent developer
6. **Preconditions:**
 - a. The particular agent template should be developed and deployed in the MAS.
 - b. The AAS of the agent type should be developed by the AAS modeling expert
7. **Postconditions:**
 - a. The agent AAS is deployed and registered in the Basyx (Dimofac) registry.
 - b. UI of the Configuration and Execution Service shows the agent type.
8. **Trigger:** The command from the UI.
9. **Main scenario:**
 - a. The agent developer uses the UI interface to provide the path to the aasx archive of the AAS and trigger the activity.
 - b. The UI component uses the AAS API to upload and register the AAS to the Basyx (Dimofac) server.
 - c. The UI component gets all the registered AASs in the system and update its view.
 - d. The information corresponding the newly deployed agent type should be added to the AAS submodel *AgentsTypes*. Note: See the description of the submodel in the section 5.5.
 - i. The property Name must correspond with the agent’s template class name.
 - ii. The Reference Element must reference to the AAS of the corresponding agent type.
10. **Extensions:**
11. **Related information:**

Figure 13 shows the use-case diagram of the “register agent type” scenario.

Figure 13 Register Agent Type Use Case

6.4 Agents activation use case

In this section we describe a workflow on how to activate the required agent. The use case diagram is shown on **Figure 14**.

1. **Use case name:** Activate agent
2. **Scope:** Configuration and Execution Service, MAS, Basyx, Kafka (Dimofac, MQTT)
3. **Primary actor:** System user
4. **Supporting actors:** Basyx (Dimofac), AMS agent of the Janus MAS, Kafka (MQTT), UI component
5. **Stakeholders:** System user
6. **Preconditions:**
 - a. The AAS of the AMS agent is active in the AAS server. The AAS registry can be used to check this.
 - b. The Janus MAS runtime with the active AMS agent should run. Check the current state of the AMS agent’s lifecycle state machine in the corresponding AAS submodel.
 - c. The required agent’s template as class should be deployed in the Janus framework.
 - d. The submodel AgentsTypes has a submodel element corresponding the agent’s type. It has the reference to the AAS of the required agent’s type.
 - e. The AAS of the required agent’s-type should be deployed in the AAS server.
 - f. The parametrization of the agent’s type should be done.
 - g. If the agent is a holon then the holon configuration should be done. For the holon configuration a BoM submodel of the holon’s type AAS is used.
 - h. All the supporting components are running (AAS registry, AAS repository, messaging middleware (Kafka, MQTT))
 - i. The AMS listens to the “ams_input_topic” for the incoming command-messages.
7. **Postconditions:**
 - a. The required agent is activated in the system.
 - b. The AAS of the activated agent should be registered to the AAS registry.
 - c. The current state of the agent’s lifecycle state machine is “Active”.
 - d. The UI of the Configuration and Execution Service shows the active agent.
8. **Trigger:** The system user activates the command from the Ui.
9. **Main scenario:**
 - a. The system user chooses in the UI the required agent type from those which present in the system
 - b. The user optionally parametrize the agent.

- i. The agent’s parametrization will be described in the separate use-case.
- c. The UI uses AAS API to write the required parameters in the corresponding AAS submodel of the agent type
- d. The user execute the command to activate the agent.
- e. The UI component calls the operation *ActivateAgent()* in the corresponding submodel of the AMS AAS. The operation *ActivateAgent()* takes the AAS ID and the type of the required agent as parameters.
- f. As a result of the this call the Basyx (Dimofac) component generates the required JSON-message and publish it through its internal kafka or mqtt publisher to the topic “ams_input_topic”.
- g. The AMS agent checks if the required agent type is available in the system by checking the *AgentTypes* submodel.
- h. The AMS agent uses the AAS ID of the required agent from the message and uses AAS API to collect the required information from the respective agent’s type AAS.
- i. Before initializing and spawning the agent the AMS registers the AAS of this agent in the AAS registry.
- j. The AMS initialize the required agent and spawns it.
- k. The Basyx (Dimofac) component notifies the UI that its registry was updated.
- l. The AMS updates its submodel *ActiveAgents*.
- m. The newly spawned agent updates its *Lifecycle* submodel
- n. The newly spawned agent checks the *assetInterfaceDescription* submodel if it needs to connect to some external interfaces.
- o. The UI component gets all the registered AASs in the system and update its view.

10. **Extensions:** error handling

11. **Related information:**

Figure 14 Activate Agent Use-Case

6.5 Agents parameterization and configuration use case

This section focuses on the workflow on how to parameterize and configure the required holon. The use case diagram is shown on **Figure 15**.

1. **Use case name:** Agents parameterization and configuration
2. **Scope:** Configuration and Execution Service
3. **Primary actor:** System user, system integrator
4. **Supporting actors:** Basyx (Dimofac), UI component, AMS Agent, Semantic Model Service
5. **Stakeholders:** System user, system integrator
6. **Preconditions:**
 - a. The particular agent template should be developed and deployed in the MAS.
 - b. The AAS of the agent type should be developed by the AAS modeling expert.
 - c. All the parameters required for the successful initialization of the agent must be presented in the AAS.
 - d. If the agent is a holon then the submodel BillOfMaterial must exist in the AAS to enable holon's configuration.
 - e. The AAS of the agent type should be deployed and registered in the AAS middleware
7. **Postconditions:**
 - a. The elements of the AAS of the agent type that represent the parameters of the agent are provided with the values.
 - b. The values of the parameters are proved for correctness and consistency.
8. **Trigger:** Fields and commands of the UI.
9. **Main scenario:**
 - a. The UI component provides the user with the view of the agent type parameterization and configuration service.
 - b. The system user or the integrator uses the UI elements to set the required parameters.
 - i. If the system is equipped with the semantic model of the agent it may provide the advanced user support regarding the agent parameterization
 - ii. At least the entered values should be checked to comply with the parameters types and ranges.
 - c. The UI component uses the AAS REST API to update the parameters
 - d. If the agent is a holon the user may provide the agents types that must be spawned during instantiation of the holon.
 - e. The user may also reference the already active agents to be included in the holon.

- i. The system must check if it is possible to include them in the holon without the conflicts with the other holons.
 - f. For the holon’s configuration the UI component updates the holon’s BillOfMaterial SM and calls the CheckHolonConfiguration() operation on the AAS.
 - g. The AAS server notifies the AMS Agent to check the holon’s configuration
 - h. The AMS Agent reads the information from the BillOfMaterial SM and uses this information to check the consistency of the configuration.
10. **Extensions:**
- a. Knowledge-based support described in [13] for the advanced user assistance
11. **Related information:**

Figure 15 Agents Parameterization and Configuration Use-Case

7 Prototypical implementation

In this section two prototypical implementations of the execution and parametrization service based on the AMS Agent are described. Though the prototypes are small, they are used to check the feasibility of the concept.

7.1 Agent Management System BaSyx Prototype

The Agent Management System BaSyx Prototype is developed on four major technology components (see Figure 16):

- The Eclipse BaSyx Middleware for hosting an Agent Management Asset Administration Shell that is necessary to configure the whole System.
- The Janus SARL Framework to develop an Agent Management System.
- Apache Kafka to communicate between the Agent Management System and the appropriate AAS in an event-based matter.
- Docker for deployment and orchestrating the spawned Agents.

Figure 16 Agent Management System BaSyx Prototype

The Eclipse BaSyx middleware implements the concepts of the AAS and offers specified AAS and SM elements according to the underlying metamodel as well as containerized AAS Registry and AAS Servers. For BaSyx the Java SDK v1.2⁵ is used that implements the AAS specification described by [14] v.2.0.1⁶. Basyx Components are usually hosted with an REST API with the appropriate API definition described at SwaggerHub⁷. Containerized BaSyx components are available in the BaSyx Repository⁸ or at Dockerhub⁹.

For the AAS infrastructure, the AAS Registry container is used unmodified. For the AAS Server, the server needs to be built from scratch since it needs the necessary dependencies associated with the operation logic. The modelled AMS AAS is loaded as **aasx* file with the *AASXToMetamodelConverter*. The modelled Spawn and Delete Operation intends to spawn or delete agents of the MAS. The Operations logic is achieved by setting the Operation invocable using Java Functional Interfaces. The Operations implement the Apache Kafka Producer that sends the parsed InputArguments (ID and Type) to the topics and the broker defined in the *AssetInterfaceDescription* Submodel.

The AMS defined in the Janus SARL Framework is configured by the hosted AAS and subscribes to the same broker and required topics. The configuration is achieved by setting up a Janus SARL Skill that derives data from the AAS and acts as a connector. In this sense, the Skill implementation may be changed to use another Version of the AAS like the newly developed v3.0.5RC02¹⁰. This enables flexibility regarding the Meta Model or the communication technology to access the AAS. After receiving an order, the AMS verifies if it should follow the order. For this purpose, the AMS explores the registry to find a description of the corresponding

⁵ <https://github.com/eclipse-basyx/basyx-java-sdk>

⁶ <https://projects.eclipse.org/projects/technology.basyx/releases/1.0.0-java>

⁷ <https://app.swaggerhub.com/organizations/BaSyx>

⁸ <https://github.com/eclipse-basyx/basyx-java-components/tree/main/basyx.components/basyx.components.docker>

⁹ <https://hub.docker.com/u/eclipsebasyx>

¹⁰ <https://github.com/admin-shell-io/aas-specs>

ID and Type. Depending on if the configuration is valid and the agent type definition fits into the existing MAS, the agent is spawned inside a new docker container that is maintained by the AMS. The configuration for the new agent is passed using environment variables.

7.2 Agent Management System Dimofac Prototype

The Agent Management System Dimofac Prototype is developed from the following major technology components (see Figure 17):

Figure 17 Agent Management System Dimofac Prototype

- The Dimofac Platform for hosting an Agent Management Asset Administration Shell that is necessary to configure the whole System. The Dimofac middleware provides the services comparable to the Basyx and complies to the standard AAS REST API, defined in [15]. It also provides the AAS registry and repository and a built in MQTT broker.
- The Janus SARL Framework to develop an Agent Management System.

- MQTT is use as a message-based communication middleware between the Agents and their AASs.

The prototype partially implements the use-case defined in 6.4. The UI functionality is not taken into account. The Dimofac Digital Platform is delivered as a Docker container and needs minimum configuration, which is made through the *docker-compose* file. The Dimofac server communicated with the MAS4AI runtime through the MQTT pubsub middleware. The common topics must be configured in the *dimofac-mqtt-settings* file (see **Figure 18**). The configuration of the communication channels for the AMS Agent is done via *assetInterfaceDescription* submodel as it was described in 5.3.

```
submodelElement.2.aasIdShort=AMS
submodelElement.2.smIdShort=Skills
submodelElement.2.seIdShort=Skill0001.ActivateAgent
submodelElement.2.callOperationTopic=/ActivateAgent/CallOperationTopic
submodelElement.2.callOperationTimeoutInMilliseconds=30000
submodelElement.2.operationEndedTopic=/ActivateAgent/CallOperationEndTopic

submodelElement.3.aasIdShort=AMS
submodelElement.3.smIdShort=Skills
submodelElement.3.seIdShort=Skill0002.DeactivateAgent
submodelElement.3.callOperationTopic=/DeactivateAgent/CallOperationTopic
submodelElement.3.callOperationTimeoutInMilliseconds=30000
submodelElement.3.operationEndedTopic=/DeactivateAgent/CallOperationEndTopic
```

Figure 18 Dimofac MQTT Topics Configuration.

The AMS Agent AAS, as well as the AASs for the test agents, are uploaded to the Dimofac platform using the platform API.

Analogously to the Basyx prototype the self-configuration of the agent is achieved by implementing the skill that specializes the *agent_aas_interpreter* capacity, which is used for the parsing and interpretation of the standard MAS4AI submodels. Several skills can implement the same capacity. This enables the agent to work with different AAS hosting platforms.

When the operation *ActivateAgent()* is called in the AMS submodel the Dimofac server publishes the specific message with the type and id of the agent to be activated. The AMS Agent interprets the message and uses the *agent_aas_interpreter skill* to get all the required information from the agent type AAS (Agent X Type AAS on **Figure 17**). It then checks if the required agent’s class exists in the system and instances it, if it is available.

8 Conclusion

In the document the concept of execution and parameterization service was presented. It is based on the development of the special type of the agent, AMS Agent, which provides system's user with the administrative and supervision services. Another key component of the service is the AAS of the AMS Agent, which serves as a single source of information about the execution and parameterization service and provides the operations to administer the system. The AAS serves as a façade between the UI and the AMS service, thus providing a good decoupling through the standard AAS API. All the parameterization and configuration information needed for the particular agent type is stored in its AAS, providing the agent's self-description capabilities. This improves the scalability and extension of the system.

The deliverable provides the list of the use-case diagrams to serve as the manuals for the developers to implement the fully functional service complying with the requirements, defined in this deliverable.

The last section of the deliverable describes two prototypical implementations of the concept for two different AAS platforms, the Basyx and the Dimofac, as well as different messaging middlewares, Kafka and MQTT. This shows the applicability and flexibility of the proposed approach for configuring and supervising of the MAS4AI agents.

9 Literature

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